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PROBIOTIC USE AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE: MARKET OVERVIEW AND PRELIMINARY SCREENING

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The use of probiotics is steadily increasing, with these products commonly marketed as dietary supplements and, in some cases, as medicinal products. This study provides a brief overview of probiotics currently available on the Serbian market and investigates antibiotic resistance in five food supplements and one medicinal product. Market analysis of probiotic products in Serbia revealed significant variability in colony-forming unit (CFU) counts and a wide range of health claims, some of which are medicinal claims. Lactobacilli were the most frequently identified microorganisms, commonly found in products sold both in pharmacies and online. Experimental findings confirmed the presence of antibiotic-resistant strains among various *Lactobacillus* species in these products. While probiotics offer health benefits, their potential role in spreading antibiotic resistance must not be overlooked. Therefore, regulatory frameworks should be updated to mandate antimicrobial resistance (AMR) screening for probiotic products, accompanied by clear guidelines for their safe use and disposal.

Key words: probiotic; antibiotic resistance; market analysis; antibiotic resistance screening; dietary supplements; *Lactobacillus*